

AN ELASTIC SOLUTION FOR A NEW NOTCHED RESIDUAL STRESS SPECIMEN SUBJECTED TO AN ANTI-CLASTIC LOADING

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ABSTRACT

A new test specimen has been proposed to explore the mechanical properties of thermoset resin exposed to residual stresses induced by curing and thermal expansion. The test principle is based on anti-clastic bending of a plate with a hole. An elastic solution to the bending problem is derived in this paper based on Reissner plate theory.

1 INTRODUCTION

Examining and quantifying the effect from residual stresses on some of the mechanical properties of composite materials are essential for enhancing the current understanding of these materials and their further use.

Residual stresses in thermoset based fibrous composite materials are built-up during curing of the matrix constituent. These stresses arise due to a miss match in straining behaviour between the fibre and matrix. The magnitude of the residual stresses may be predicted from a thermo-mechanical modelling approach [1-4]. In addition experimental methods to characterise the induced residual stresses exists and has been reported by several authors [5, 6]. However less effort has been made to explain the influence from the residual stresses on the mechanical properties [7, 8].

To mature the gap between characterising the residual stress state in the material and the actual effect on the mechanical properties an anti-clastic bending loading of a flat plate residual stress specimen is proposed as a test configuration. It is previously showed that this type of specimen is able to induce a well-defined biaxial residual stress state in its gauge area [9]. A sketch of this particular specimen configuration and the proposed anti-clastic loading is shown in Fig-1.

Figure 1. A sketch of the residual stress specimen subjected to an anti-clastic bending. The hole/notch in the center serves two purposes; 1) Quantification of the residual stress state in the material 2) Provide a known location for failure initiation during mechanical loading.

A local solution is derived by establishing the elastic solution for the stress state in the residual stress plate without a hole. The derived stress state in the gauge area is used as boundary condition for a local solution containing a notch/hole. The local solution is approximated by an in-plane loaded plate having a circular hole. At the top and bottom surfaces of the plate a plane stress condition exists and a local solution relying on the stress state near a hole in an infinite plate subjected to a boundary stress would approximate the actual stress state in the specimen.

The local solution for the stress state in the notched gauge area of the residual stress specimen may be used to quantify the effect from the residual stresses on some of the mechanical properties i.e. the fatigue endurance level and notch sensitivity.

2 ELASTIC SOLUTION

The analytical solution for the specimen derived in this paper is based on the assumptions from the “Reissner” plate theory. This implies that the in-plane stress components σ_{rr} , $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ and $\sigma_{r\theta}$ varies linearly through the thickness. The out of plane shear stresses is described by a parabolic distribution through the thickness.

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{rr} &= \frac{12 M_r z}{h^3} \quad , \quad \sigma_{\theta\theta} = \frac{12 M_\theta z}{h^3} \quad , \quad \sigma_{r\theta} = -\frac{12 M_{r\theta} z}{h^3} \\ \sigma_{rz} &= \frac{3 Q_r}{2h} \left\{ 1 - \left(\frac{2z}{h} \right)^2 \right\} \quad , \quad \sigma_{\theta z} = \frac{3 Q_\theta}{2h} \left\{ 1 - \left(\frac{2z}{h} \right)^2 \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

According to the Reissner approach the deflection (w) and the mid surface rotation (φ_r and φ_θ) are formulated as an average of the through the thickness deformation. The total thickness is denoted (h) and z is the out of plane coordinate.

The specimen comprises of a central region denoted (region #1) where a small hole is present. The focus is to derive a solution for the stress state at the edge of this hole. The outer region (region #2) consists of a sandwiched metallic plate in between neat polymer layers. The outer region has the purpose to restrict the free deformation of the region #1 during curing of the neat polymer/composite material meaning that residual stresses are formed. The mechanical problem illustrated in Figure-1 is solved in a cylindrical coordinate frame and dimensions are illustrated in Figure-2.

Figure 2. Sketch of the model used for building the solution. A central and outer region denoted #1 and #2. The model is loaded mechanically at the edges by moments (M_{ij}) and out of plane shear forces (Q_i). Radial dimensions are denoted ρ (hole radii), $R1$ and $R2$.

The loading of the model in its four corners (see Figure-1) is equivalent to load shown in Figure-2 with moments and out of plane shear forces described solely through the coordinate (θ).

In the absence of any surface load ($q=0$) and further setting the auxiliary stress function to zero ($\Psi = 0$). This further makes the out of plane shear force resultants (Q_r and Q_t) equal to the Kirchhoff formulation. The simplification made enables the stress resultants to be described through the deflection alone (see Eq-2 to -4).

$$Q_r := \left(- \left(\frac{\partial^3}{\partial r^3} w(r, \theta) \right) - \frac{\frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} w(r, \theta)}{r} + \frac{2 \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} w(r, \theta) \right)}{r^3} - \frac{\frac{\partial^3}{\partial \theta^2 \partial r} w(r, \theta)}{r^2} + \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial r} w(r, \theta)}{r^2} \right)_{BS} \quad (2)$$

$$Q_t := \left(- \frac{\frac{\partial^3}{\partial \theta \partial r^2} w(r, \theta)}{r} - \frac{\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta \partial r} w(r, \theta)}{r^2} - \frac{\frac{\partial^3}{\partial \theta^3} w(r, \theta)}{r^3} \right)_{BS}$$

where BS is the bending stiffness which in the central region (region #1) is $Eh^3/(12(1 - \nu^2))$. The bending stiffness in the outer region (region #2) may be determined using sandwich plate approach.

$$\begin{aligned}
 Mrr := & \left(- \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} w(r, \theta) \right) - \frac{v \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} w(r, \theta) \right)}{r^2} - \frac{v \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} w(r, \theta) \right)}{r} \right. \\
 & + \left(- \frac{1}{5} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial r^4} w(r, \theta) - \frac{1}{5} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial r^3} \frac{w(r, \theta)}{r} + \frac{2}{5} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} \frac{w(r, \theta)}{r^2} \right. \\
 & + \frac{4}{5} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \theta^2 \partial r} \frac{w(r, \theta)}{r^3} - \frac{6}{5} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} \frac{w(r, \theta)}{r^4} \\
 & \left. \left. - \frac{1}{5} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \theta^2 \partial r^2} \frac{w(r, \theta)}{r^2} - \frac{2}{5} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \frac{w(r, \theta)}{r^3} \right) h^2 \right)_{BS} \\
 \\
 Mtt := & \left(\left(- \frac{1}{5} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \theta^2 \partial r^2} \frac{w(r, \theta)}{r^2} - \frac{1}{5} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \theta^4} \frac{w(r, \theta)}{r^4} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. - \frac{1}{5} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \theta^2 \partial r} \frac{w(r, \theta)}{r^3} \right) h^2 - v \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} w(r, \theta) \right) - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} \frac{w(r, \theta)}{r^2} \right. \\
 & \left. \left. - \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \frac{w(r, \theta)}{r} \right) \right)_{BS} \tag{3}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 Mrt := & \left(\left(\frac{1}{5} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \theta \partial r^3} \frac{w(r, \theta)}{r} + \frac{1}{5} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \theta^3 \partial r} \frac{w(r, \theta)}{r^3} \right. \right. \\
 & + \frac{1}{10} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \theta \partial r^2} \frac{w(r, \theta)}{r^2} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \theta^3} \frac{w(r, \theta)}{r^4} \\
 & \left. \left. - \frac{3}{10} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta \partial r} \frac{w(r, \theta)}{r^3} \right) h^2 + \frac{(1-v) \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta \partial r} w(r, \theta) \right)}{r} \right. \\
 & \left. \left. - \frac{(1-v) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} w(r, \theta) \right)}{r^2} \right) \right)_{BS}
 \end{aligned}$$

Notice that the moments do depend on the plate thickness which makes the formulation different from Kirchhoff's formulation. However when ($h=0$) the formulation for the moments reduces to the Kirchhoff's formulation.

Since the auxiliary stress function is set to zero one less boundary condition can be fulfilled and therefore Kirchhoff's effective shear force is used (V_r).

$$V_r := Q_r - \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} M_{rt} \tag{4}$$

In the absence of any surface load the governing plate equation is identical for classical plate theory (see Eq-5).

$$\Delta\Delta w = 0 \quad (5)$$

As explained previously the plate consists of two domains and a solution for the deflection in each domain satisfying the governing plate equation (Eq-5) is proposed as stated in Eq-6.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Region-1:} \quad w^{(\#1)} &= B0 + \left(B1 r^2 + B2 + \frac{B3}{r^2} \right) \sin(2\theta) \\ \text{Region-2:} \quad w^{(\#2)} &= C0 + \left(C1 r^2 + C2 + \frac{C3}{r^2} \right) \sin(2\theta) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Eight constants (B0...B3 and C0...C3) need to be determined utilising boundary and continuity conditions. These conditions are presented in Eq-7.

$$\begin{aligned} M_{rr}^{(\#1)}(r = \rho, \theta) &= 0 \\ V_r^{(\#1)}(r = \rho, \theta) &= 0 \\ M_{rr}^{(\#1)}(r = R_1, \theta) &= M_r^{(\#2)}(r = R_1, \theta) \\ V_r^{(\#1)}(r = R_1, \theta) &= V_r^{(\#2)}(r = R_1, \theta) \\ w^{(\#1)}(r = R_1, \theta) &= w^{(\#2)}(r = R_1, \theta) \\ \frac{\partial w^{(\#1)}(r = R_1, \theta)}{\partial r} &= \frac{\partial w^{(\#2)}(r = R_1, \theta)}{\partial r} \\ M_{rt}^{(\#2)}(r = R_2, \theta) &= -\frac{1}{2}P\cos(2\theta) \\ w^{(\#2)}(r = R_2, \pi/4) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The edge moment (M_{rt}) is used as a boundary condition (see Eq-7). However, one of the other stress resultants could be used as well.

The coefficients in Eq-6 may be determined by solving the system of algebraic equations in Eq-7. The coefficients become quit vast expression and for that reason they are not written out in its full form.

Analytical expression for the residual stress state (σ_0) in the central region (#1) has previously been established [9] and may be superimposed to the expressions for the bending stresses in Eq-1. The residual stresses derived in [9] are valid under the assumption of linear elastic and isotropic material behaviour. Under these assumptions the residual stress state is axe-symmetric and therefor only depends on the radial coordinate (r) (cf. Eq-8).

$$\sigma_{rr} = \begin{cases} -\frac{\sigma_0}{\Gamma} \left(1 - \frac{\rho^2}{r^2} \right) & \rho < r < R1 \\ \frac{\sigma_0}{\Gamma} \frac{\left(1 - \frac{\rho^2}{R1^2} \right)}{\left(1 - \frac{R1^2}{R2^2} \right)} \left(1 - \frac{R2^2}{r^2} \right) \frac{R1^2}{R2^2} & R1 < r < R2 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma_{\theta\theta} = \begin{cases} -\frac{\sigma_0}{\Gamma} \left(1 + \frac{\rho^2}{r^2}\right) & \rho < r < R1 \\ \frac{\sigma_0}{\Gamma} \frac{\left(1 - \frac{\rho^2}{R1^2}\right)}{\left(1 - \frac{R1^2}{R2^2}\right)} \left(1 + \frac{R2^2}{r^2}\right) \frac{R1^2}{R2^2} & R1 < r < R2 \end{cases}$$

$$\Gamma = \frac{\rho^2}{R1^2} - 1 + \frac{(\alpha - 1) \left(1 - \frac{r^2}{R2^2}\right) \rho^2}{R1^2 \left(\alpha + 1 - 2\beta \left(1 - \frac{r^2}{R2^2}\right)\right)}$$

In Eq-8 α and β are Dundurs parameters describing the elastic miss match in a Bi-material problem [10]. Previously the induced residual stress state (σ_0) for this type of specimen using neat epoxy has been measured to 4-6MPa with a chosen set of process parameters [9].

3 ANALYTICAL RESULTS

Using the obtained solution the deflection of the specimen is evaluated and shown in Figure-3. The deflection in the center of the model is compared with a full 3D FE solution. A relatively large discrepancy is seen but currently an explanation for this has not been found.

Figure 3. The deflection of the specimen assuming $\rho = 2mm$ and $h = 2mm$.

The radial behavior of radial and tangential moments (M_r and M_θ) and the effective shear force (V_r) are graphically shown in Figure-4.

Figure 4. Stress resultants in Region-1. The radial moment (M_r) and the effective shear force (V_r) yields zero at the edge of the hole, whereas tangential moment (M_θ) display a steep gradient in vicinity of the hole.

From Figure-4 it is seen that the tangential moment (M_θ) is concentrated around the hole whereas M_r and V_r are zero, as expected. It is therefore believed that the concentration of tangential bending stresses will failure in the specimen, and the collective effect of tangential stresses due to bending and residual stresses can be studied, see also [9].

The stress concentration at the edge of the hole is, when applying the Reissner plate theory, depending on the hole radii to plate thickness (see Figure-5). Comparing the stress concentration factor (k_θ) with similar results from the FE solution a good match has been achieved. For comparison the stress concentration factor obtained applying the Kirchhoff is shown in the Figure-5. It may be seen that the stress concentration factor is in depended on the hole radii to plate thickness ratio and will yield some error for small ratios.

Figure 5. Tangential stress concentration factor at the hole. The classical plate theory “Kirchhoff” display a constant concentration factor whereas the “Reissner” plate theory display a dependence on the ratio (ρ/h).

4 NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

A numerical example is presented where it is assumed that the specimen is made from neat epoxy and having the 1mm thick steel reinforcement in region #2. The total specimen thickness is set to 2mm. The hole radii is 2.5mm. As stated earlier it is realistic to obtain a residual stress state $\sigma_0 = 5MPa$ with this setup. With the given $\frac{\rho}{h} = 1.25$ the stress concentration factor from the mechanical loading alone yield $k_{mech} = 1.79$ (see Fig-5). The stress concentration from the residual stress state yields $k_{\sigma_0} = 1.98$. Superimposing the mechanical and residual stress states yields the total stress in the specimen. In a quasi-static loading scenario the specimen is predicted to fail at the edge of the hole due to tangential stresses at this location (see Fig-6).

Figure 6. The tangential stresses near the hole including a superimposed 5MPa residual stress state. An ultimate tensile strength of 75MPa is stated in the datasheet. Loading the specimen to failure the residual stress state will only cover a minor portion of the total stress state.

In this case the residual stress state covers about 13% of the total stress at the edge of the hole prior to failure. Even though this is a relative small portion it should be possible to measure this reduction in material strength and compare it to neat material strength (samples without a steel reinforcement/residual stresses).

However the measurable impact from a residual stress in a fatigue loading scenario may be enforced since the ratio between the residual stresses to the mechanical stresses will larger and possible in the range up to 50% (or maybe even higher). Therefore it is expected that the residual stress specimen will have a large potential for studying the fatigue behavior of neat polymer and fiber composite materials when residual stresses are present in the material.

4 CONCLUSION

An analytical solution for stress state in a newly proposed residual stress specimen subjected to an anti-clastic bending loading condition has been presented. This solution together with previously established solution for the residual stress state build up during curing creates the complete elastic solution for the specimen.

Having a solution that decouples the mechanical and residual stresses makes the specimen useful for studying the effects from manufacturing process conditions, through the residual stresses, on e.g. the fatigue endurance on a polymer or fiber composite material.

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